

A NEW DESIGN METHOD
FOR STRUCTURES OF LAMINATE CONSTRUCTION

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Introduction

The British chemical industry has now been making use of glass-fibre reinforced plastics (GRP) for almost twenty years. These materials have proved very useful, with a wide range of corrosion resistance and adequate mechanical properties: they are easy to fabricate but require a thorough understanding if they are to be used with maximum reliability and economy.

The first commercially available GRP tanks were not designed at all, in the engineering sense: they were simply copies of their steel counterparts. Some difficulties in manufacture and failures in service were encountered; these highlighted gaps in our knowledge of the behaviour of the materials, and led to improved appreciation of their unique properties and of the differences between GRP and other materials.

This paper deals primarily with the design of tanks and pressure vessels in GRP, but the design principles are applicable to any type of laminar construction and to any type of engineering structure. The design method has been codified in the British Standard for Vessels and Tanks in Reinforced Plastics (Ref. 1), which was issued towards the end of 1973: since some large U.K. fabricators and users were making use of the method before its formal publication, almost three years satisfactory experience with it can now be claimed.

Traditional Pressure Vessel Design

Most countries have developed their own pressure vessel Code for vessels in steel and other metal alloys, and the general

basis for design in all of them is the concept of a 'design stress' - that is, load per unit cross-section area (Figure 1a)-which must not be exceeded in service. This design stress is arrived at by taking some specific and easily measured property of the material (ultimate tensile strength, for example) and dividing it by a design factor, which takes into account such things as variability of plate properties, welded joint efficiency and the likely extent of corrosion in service.

Among the Codes using this method are BS.1500 and BS.1515 (Ref.2) in the U.K., ASME (Ref. 3) in the USA, and the AD Merkblätter (Ref. 4) in Germany. There is also a draft international Code (Ref. 5) in the course of preparation.

The design procedures in these Codes must be regarded as satisfactory, since a very large number of steel pressure vessels is in successful use throughout the world. As a result, attempts were made to use the same procedure for the design of GRP vessels, and some Code documents, notably the German AD Merkblatt N1 (Ref. 6) and ASME Section X (Ref. 7), have been written in this way. Successful vessels can undoubtedly be designed, but large design factors are required to allow for such variables as the directional properties of the reinforcement, the loss of properties which occurs with time in most GRP laminates and the effect of repeated load applications. The shortcomings of the technique show most obviously in dealing with 'stress concentrations' (such as around branches, at points of support or in knuckle radii of dished ends) and it is at such points that vessel failure is most likely to occur. Further, all the Codes using design stress as a basic criterion make the assumptions that :

- i) the material is approximately isotropic, and
- ii) the properties are uniform through the material thickness.

In general, neither of these assumptions is valid in the case of GRP laminate constructions, where it is most likely that different layers will have differing mechanical properties. Indeed, one of the advantages of GRP is the ease with which a few extra layers of reinforcement, or a different type of reinforcement with higher strength, can be added at positions where the load is high.

The "Unit Load" Concept

Consideration of the properties of laminate layers led to the realisation that design should be based, not on "stress" (load per unit cross sectional area), but on "unit load", which is the load per unit width of a single laminate layer of unit glass content (Figure 1b).

It has been found experimentally that the unit load which will just cause fracture - called the "ultimate unit strength" - does not depend at all on the resin/glass ratio, for a given type of laminate layer, over the normally used range of ratios. Examples of the experimental work leading to this conclusion may be found in papers to the International Reinforced Plastics

Conferences of the British Plastics Federation, notably those by O'Connor (Ref. 8) and Raymond (Ref. 9). Relevant data from these papers is reproduced here as Figures 2 and 3, respectively.

For design purposes, therefore, we may use a single value of ultimate unit strength for all layers of a given type in a laminate (Table 1).

Table 1: Properties of Reinforced Laminate Layers

Type of Reinforcement	Ultimate Tensile Unit Strength	Extensibility	Lap shear strength
Units	N/mm width (per kg/m ² glass)	N/mm width (per kg/m ² glass)	N/mm ²
Chopped strand mat	200	12,700	7.0
Woven rovings (warp and weft directions)	300	16,200	7.0

Where directionally-oriented reinforcements are used as, for example, in the use of woven rovings or wound filaments :- either (a) the ultimate tensile unit load and extensibility values to be used must be determined by the testing of sample laminates laid up with the fibres in the same direction, relative to the applied load, as will be used in the structure under design, or (b) the appropriate values are obtained by multiplying the σ_0 value by a factor for the fibre angle concerned. These factors are determined previously by tests, and are shown on a polar diagram (Figure 4).

It has also been noted experimentally that the load at which a sample of laminate will fracture is very close to the fracture load calculated from the ultimate unit strengths of the individual layers making up the laminate. When tested in tension, with care being taken to minimise bending loads in the test specimens, the reproducibility of this type of test is good - normally better than $\pm 10\%$.

The various steps involved in the determination of the loads which have to be carried in the various parts of the vessel, the calculation of the permissible unit loadings for the various laminate layers, and hence an acceptable laminate construction, are set out in the form of charts in Figures 5, 6 and 7.

For design purposes, the ultimate unit load is divided by a design factor, K, to determine the "allowable unit loading", which is limited by laminate strength (u_L). The design factor is the product of a series of part factors, each accounting for the effect of one of the variables encountered in manufacture or operation of the vessel. In the British Standard design method, there are six such part factors, thus :-

- i) a numerical factor (β), representing the factor of safety on ultimate strength,
- ii) K_1 , a factor relating to the method of manufacture and varying between 1.4 and 3,
- iii) K_2 , a factor relating to long-term behaviour, varying between 1.2 and 2,
- iv) K_3 , a factor relating to operating temperature, varying between 1 and 1.25,
- v) K_4 , a factor relating to cyclic loading, varying between 1.1 (for up to 1,000 load applications in the vessel life) and 2 (for 1,000,000 load applications),
- vi) K_5 , a factor relating to the curing procedure, varying between 1.1 and 1.5.

The overall design factor K may thus vary between 6 and about 40, a typical value for usual designs of vessel being in the range 8 to 15.

Strain

In the design of pressure vessels in metallic materials, a reasonable ductility is normally assumed. Typically, extensions to failure in a tensile test for common constructional materials will be 20% or more, the bulk of the extension being plastic strain. Where brittle fracture is possible (as in the case of mild steel equipment operated at low temperatures), special precautions are taken at both design and fabrication stages to ensure safe operation of the equipment.

The load-extension curve obtained during tensile testing of GRP differs from the typical curves for metals in three important respects (Fig. 8) :-

- i) the slope of the elastic portion of the curve is much lower: that is, the specific stiffness of the material is much less,
- ii) irregularities occur in the curve at relatively low strain values - typically about 0.3% - indicating that laminate damage by debonding or resin cracking is beginning to occur, and
- iii) in the "plastic" range, the load increases continuously to fracture, while continuing laminate damage occurs: the fracture strain is much lower than that typical for ductile metals.

It is necessary to take account of these characteristics in the design procedure and the method adopted for this is to make use of a specific stiffness parameter, called "extensibility", which is dependent on the actual weight of glass present, and independent of the glass/resin ratio of the layer, within the usual limits, just as the ultimate tensile unit strength is. Extensibility values are thus quoted "per unit weight of glass", and are unique for each type of reinforcement (Table 1).

The allowable unit loading (u), which is limited by ductility criteria, is determined for each type of reinforcement

in the laminate, by multiplying the extensibility for that type of layer by the permissible strain. This permissible strain is dictated by the ductility (as measured by extension to failure) of the unreinforced resin: the B.S. criterion is a permissible strain of 0.2% or 10% of the resin extension to failure, whichever is less (Figure 5).

The Design Method

So far, we have determined two "allowable unit loadings", one (u_L) from the strength of the laminate layer and one (u_S) from stiffness/ductility criteria, for each type of layer to be incorporated in the proposed laminate. From these two, a "design unit loading" (u_x) is next determined (Figure 6). In some cases it will simply be the lesser of u_S and u_L : in other cases, a further calculation to equate the strains in all the layers making up the laminate is necessary.

Having thus determined the design unit loadings, for each type of layer, the overall laminate design can be commenced. It is essential that the sum of the load carrying capacities of the layers making up the laminate must be at least equal to the actual load to be carried. Expressed mathematically this is :-

$$u_1 w_1 n_1 + u_2 w_2 n_2 + \dots + u_x w_x n_x \geq Q \quad (1)$$

where u_x = design unit loading for layer of type x

w_x = weight of reinforcement per unit area in one layer of type x

n_x = number of layers of type x in laminate proposed

Q = maximum applied unit load (i.e. maximum force per unit width) to be carried by the laminate (Figures 7 and 8).

It should be noted that the design formulae are all applicable with any consistent series of units: if S.I. units are in use, Q will be expressed in N/mm, w in kg/m² glass and u in N/mm per kg/m² glass.

BS.4994 gives details of methods for the determination of Q in various parts of a vessel. For example, the hoop unit load in a cylindrical vessel is determined from thin shell theory (Ref.10) using an expression :-

$$Q_c = \frac{pDi}{2} \quad (2)$$

where Q_c = maximum circumferential unit load due to applied pressure,

p = total effective pressure (N/mm² in S.I. units) at point of vessel under consideration

Di = inner diameter of shell (mm in S.I. units)

Similarly, formulae are given for determining the maximum axial unit load in the shell, the unit loads in domed ends of standard shapes (hemispherical, torispherical & semi-ellipsoidal), in bolted flat covers, at flanged joints, and around openings and

branches. In every case, provided that the appropriate "Q" can be determined from the vessel geometry and operating conditions, a laminate that will make the best possible use of the reinforcement to be incorporated can be designed. This is probably best demonstrated by the use of examples.

Example of Shell Design for Internal Pressure

Consider the design of a cylindrical vessel of 1,000 mm (3 ft. 3 in.) internal diameter, for a total effective pressure of 2 bars gauge (30 psi or 0.2 N/mm²).

The hoop unit load will be

$$Q_c = \frac{0.2 \times 1,000}{2} = 100 \text{ N/mm}$$

and, for the purpose of this example, we will assume that the maximum axial unit load in the shell does not exceed this value. In practice, calculations involving bending between supports (for horizontal vessels) or due to wind or other external loads (for vertical vessels) would be necessary to determine the maximum axial unit load, and the weight of vessel and contents also has to be taken into account.

For the determination of the design factor K, we make the following assumptions (these varying, of course, in different practical cases) :-

- i) the vessel is to be made by the hand lay-up technique, so that $K_1 = 1.6$,
- ii) because of lack of relevant experience K_2 , the factor relating to long-term behaviour, is chosen as 2,
- iii) the operating temperature of the vessel is 40°C below the heat distortion temperature of the resin, so that K_3 is 1,
- iv) the only repeated loadings are represented by occasional filling and emptying, so that $K_4 = 1.1$,
- v) the vessel is to be fully post-cured by heating after fabrication, and this permits a value of 1.1 for K_5 .

The overall design factor is thus :-

$$K = 3 \times 1.6 \times 2 \times 1 \times 1.1 \times 1.1 = 11.6$$

1. All-CSM Construction

If the vessel is to be constructed entirely of resin and chopped strand mat layers, the design procedure is now as follows: The 'load-limited' allowable unit loading (u_L) is determined from

$$u_L = \frac{\text{ultimate tensile unit strength for CSM}}{\text{design factor (K)}} \\ = \frac{200}{11.6} = 17.2 \text{ N/mm (per kg/m}^2 \text{ glass).}$$

The 'strain limited' allowable unit loading (u_s) is determined from $u_s = (\text{extensibility for CSM}) \times (\text{allowable strain})$. If we assume a resin with an extension to failure greater than 2% (unreinforced), then the allowable strain will be 0.2%, and

$$\begin{aligned} u_s &= 12,700 \times 0.2 \times 10^{-2} \\ &= 25.4 \text{ N/mm (per kg/m}^2 \text{ glass)} \end{aligned}$$

Since u_L is less than u_s , the design may be said to be 'load-limited', and the u_L value is therefore taken as the design unit loading. The design will normally be 'strain-limited' when either :

- (a) a comparatively brittle resin is selected (perhaps because of its particular chemical resistance), or
- (b) the method of manufacture and working conditions lead to a low design factor, K.

When the laminate being designed is actually loaded with 17.2 N/mm, the actual strain will be $\frac{17.2}{12,700} = 0.14\%$, and this is the design strain for the particular vessel.

If all the laminate layers are of the same type (e.g. all-CSM as in this example) a simplified version of the main design formula may be used :-

$$Q = u (wn)$$

where (wn) is the total weight of glass required in the laminate. In our example,

$$(wn) = \frac{Q}{u} = \frac{100}{17.2} = 5.8 \text{ kg/m}^2$$

Manufacturers of GRP equipment have their own practices which will determine how a laminate containing this weight of glass may be made up. Two possible laminates which satisfy the requirements are specified in Tables 2 and 3, and illustrated in Figures 9a and 9b: either would be acceptable.

To calculate the thicknesses of the various layers, and thus the thickness of the completed laminate, the glass content (or glass-resin ratio) needs to be known. If a glass content of 30% in CSM layers is in use, the thickness expected will be 2.2 mm per kg/m^2 (from Figure 10).

Therefore, laminate A, which has a total glass content of 6.0 kg/m^2 , will have a thickness of $6.0 \times 2.2 = 13.2 \text{ mm}$ and, similarly, laminate B, with a total glass content of 5.85 kg/m^2 will be $5.85 \times 2.2 = 12.9 \text{ mm}$ thick.

Table 2 - Chopped Strand Mat Laminate 'A'

Layer Type	Weight of CSM		Layer Thickness*	Number of Layers	Total Glass Weight	Laminate Thickness
	(g/m ²)	(oz/ft ²)				
1	300	1	0.66	2 ⁺	0.6	1.32
3	600	2	1.32	9	5.4	11.88
Totals	-	-	-	11	6.0	13.2

Table 3 - Chopped Strand Mat Laminate 'B'

Layer Type	Weight of CSM		Layer Thickness*	Number of Layers	Total Glass Weight	Laminate Thickness
	(g/m ²)	(oz/ft ²)				
1	300	1	0.66	2 ⁺	0.6	1.32
2	450	1½	0.99	5	2.25	4.95
3	600	2	1.32	5	3.0	6.6
Totals	-	-	-	12	5.85	12.9

Notes for Tables 2 and 3 * assumes a glass content of 30% by weight
 + one layer at each surface.

2. Mat and Rovings Construction

In practice, a vessel of the type under consideration would probably be made using alternate layers of chopped strand mat and woven rovings as reinforcement, because of the high load-carrying capacity of the rovings in their warp and weft directions. A typical construction might be alternate layers of cloth rovings (with the fibres correctly aligned in hoop and axial directions where unit loads are highest) and 450 g/m² ("1½ oz") mat. A layer of 300 g/m² ("1 oz") mat would normally be incorporated at each surface, and another 600 g/m² ("2 oz") mat would be provided at the inside to support the corrosion-resisting gel coat.

The laminate would then be calculated by the following procedure. Making the same assumptions as before, K = 11.6 and the allowable unit loadings for the chopped strand mat layers will be u_L = 17.2 and u_S = 25.4 N/mm (per kg/m² glass) as in example 1 above. The corresponding values for the woven rovings will be :-

$$u_L = \frac{300}{11.6} = 25.8 \text{ N/mm}$$

$$u_S = 16,200 \times 0.2 \times 10^{-2} = 32.4 \text{ N/mm.}$$

For both types of layer, u_L is smaller than u_s , so that the design is again load-limited. However, where mixed layers are employed, it is necessary to calculate on the basis of equal strain to avoid overloading the weaker layers.

When each layer is loaded with the allowable unit loading, u_L , the strains will be :-

$$\text{for CSM} \quad E_L = \frac{17.2}{12,700} = 0.14\% \text{ (as in example 1)}$$

$$\text{for WR} \quad E_L = \frac{25.8}{16,200} = 0.16\%$$

Since the CSM layers will be overloaded if the strain in the laminate is permitted to exceed 0.14%, the strain in the layers of rovings must also be limited to this value. At this design strain, the design unit loadings will be

$$\text{for CSM} \quad u_x = 17.2 \text{ N/mm (per kg/m}^2 \text{ glass)}$$

$$\text{for WR} \quad u_x = \frac{25.8 \times 0.14}{0.16} = 22.6 \text{ N/mm (per kg/m}^2 \text{ glass)}$$

The laminate construction may now be determined from formula (1)

$$\begin{array}{rcl} u_1 w_1 n_1 & + & u_2 w_2 n_2 & + & u_3 w_3 n_3 & \geq & Q \\ 22.6 \times 0.8 n & + & 17.2 \times 0.45 (n - 1) & + & 17.2 \times 1.2 & \geq & 100 \\ n \text{ layers} & & (n - 1) \text{ layers} & & \text{surface layers} & & \\ \text{woven rovings} & & 450 \text{ g/m}^2 \text{ CSM} & & 1,200 \text{ g/m}^2 \text{ CSM} & & \end{array}$$

Solving, the minimum value of n to satisfy this condition is 3.4. Since the number of layers must be an integer, n must be taken for this construction as 4, leading to the laminate shown in Table 4 and Figure 9c. Where the calculated value of n is only slightly above a whole number, it is usually worth while to add a further 300 g/m² CSM and re-calculate: if this brings the n below the whole number, one layer of rovings and a corresponding layer of 450 g/m² CSM are saved, thus giving a more economic laminate with adequate load-carrying capacity.

It should especially be noted that the three laminates displayed in Tables 2, 3 and 4, and Figure 9, all have the same load-carrying capacity, even though their thickness varies between 8.7 mm and 13.2 mm.

Table 4 - Mixed Laminate (CSM and Rovings)

Layer Type	Reinforcement Type	Weight of Glass		Layer Thickness*	Number of Layers	Total Glass Weight	Laminate Thickness (mm)
		(g/m ²)	(oz/ft ²)				
1	Mat	300	1	0.66	2 ⁺	0.6	1.32
2	Mat	450	1½	0.99	3	1.35	2.97
3	Mat	600	2	1.32	1	0.6	1.32
4	Rovings	800	-	0.76	4	3.2	3.04
Totals	-	-	-	-	10	5.75	8.7

Notes for Table 4 * assumes a glass content of 30% by weight for CSM and 55% for rovings

+ one layer at each surface.

3. Comparison with 'Traditional' Design Method

It is of interest to compare the results obtained by use of the method described with results obtained for a similar vessel by the use of the traditional design method using the concept of stress. This can, of course, be done only for the all-CSM construction, where the layer properties may be assumed to be reasonably consistent throughout the laminate thickness.

A laminate consisting of layers of resin/chopped strand mat, having a glass content of 30% and an ultimate tensile unit strength of 200 N/mm width (per kg/m² glass), should develop on test a conventional ultimate tensile strength of approximately 12,000 psi.

Using this value of U.T.S. and a design factor of 10 leads us to a "design stress" of 1,200 psi. For a vessel to operate at 30 psi (gauge) and having an internal diameter of 40 inches (i.e. equivalent to 1,000 mm. i.d. and 2 bars design pressure), the thickness required, determined from the conventional hoop stress formula for thin cylindrical shells

$$\text{stress} = \frac{\text{pressure} \times \text{diameter}}{2 \times \text{thickness}} \quad \text{will be :}$$

$$t = \frac{30 \times 40}{2 \times 1,200} = \frac{1}{2} \text{ inch}$$

It will be noted that this result is very close to the figure of 12.9 mm, obtained by use of the unit load method in which a design factor of 11.6 was used. Smaller design factors (reflecting greater precision in manufacture and/or relatively easier operating conditions) will permit the use of smaller thicknesses, whereas more severe operating conditions require a higher design factor and, thus, a greater laminate thickness: this highly desirable flexibility in the unit load method is one of its considerable advantages.

One further benefit to be gained from its use is the

control it provides over the actual amount of reinforcement to be incorporated, rather than the thickness of the finished laminate, which is a secondary variable. Indeed, for structures where there is no possibility of compressive loads, the laminate thickness need not even be calculated, although it is useful as an inspection check during fabrication.

It is, however, necessary to calculate the thickness of the proposed laminate where compressive loads are involved, so as to ensure that the structure has adequate strength to prevent failure by buckling. The design procedure is illustrated in Figure 7, and has been fully described in an earlier paper (Ref. 11).

Conclusion

The unit load method represents a considerable technical advance in the techniques available for the design of engineering components in laminar materials. It is confidently predicted that the method will find widespread use as its advantages become more widely known.

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Figure 1 – The Concepts of Stress and Unit Loading, Demonstrated in a Rectangular Testpiece Loaded in Tension

Experimental Results

- o = Isophthalic Resin
- x = Bisphenol Resin
- (each with 1800 g/m² CSM)

Figure 2 – Experimental Basis for Minimum Ultimate Tensile Unit Load (after O'Connor)

Figure 3 – Experimental Basis for Minimum Extensibility (after Raymond)

Figure 4 – Typical properties of a mixed laminate of mat and rovings, related to Fibre Orientation

Figure 5 – Design Method, Part 1: Determination of Allowable Unit Loadings

Figure 6 – Design Method 1, Part 2
Postulation of Laminate Construction

Figure 8 – Idealised Load–Extension Curves for Various Materials

Laminate A

Laminate B

Laminate C

All three laminates have the same load-carrying capacity

Layer	Reinforcement	Wt % Glass	Thickness
1	300g/m ² CSM	30	0.66mm
2	450g/m ² CSM	30	0.99mm
3	600g/m ² CSM	30	1.32mm
4	RP 25 rovings	55	0.76mm

Figure 9 – Examples of Laminate Construction

Figure 10 – Relationship between Thickness and Glass Content